

Treatment of Unstable Intertrochanteric Femoral Fractures in Elderly Population- A Retrospective Comparison between Those Treated by PFNA vs. Primary Hemi-Arthroplasty of the Hip

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Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 15-05-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Unstable intertrochanteric femoral fractures in the elderly pose significant challenges due to the high risk of complications and mortality. Surgical treatment options, including Proximal Femoral Nail Antirootation (PFNA) and Primary Hemi-Arthroplasty of the Hip, offer varying outcomes in terms of recovery and functionality.

Aim: This study aims to compare the clinical outcomes of PFNA and Primary Hemi-Arthroplasty in treating unstable intertrochanteric femoral fractures in the elderly population.

Methods: A retrospective analysis was conducted, involving 100 elderly patients with unstable intertrochanteric femoral fractures. Patients were divided into two groups: 50 treated with Proximal Femoral Nail Antirootation (PFNA) and 50 with primary hemi-arthroplasty. The study compared postoperative complications, functional outcomes, hospital stay duration, and mortality rates.

Results: It was observed that the PFNA group had significantly fewer complications, better functional outcomes (higher Harris Hip Scores), and lower incidence of dislocation. Although hemi-arthroplasty patients had shorter hospital stays, there were no significant differences in mortality rates between the two groups. Overall, PFNA demonstrated a more favorable complication profile and better functional outcomes.

Conclusion: Both PFNA and Primary Hemi-Arthroplasty are viable options for treating Unstable intertrochanteric femoral fractures in elderly patients are a significant clinical challenge. The use of Proximal Femoral Nail Antirootation (PFNA) is often associated with shorter surgical times and less blood loss, while Primary Hemi-Arthroplasty offers superior functional outcomes in the mid-term follow-up.

Recommendations: It is recommended that future prospective studies include larger sample sizes and extended follow-up periods to validate these results and gain a deeper understanding of the long-term advantages and disadvantages of each surgical technique.

Keywords: Unstable intertrochanteric femoral fractures, PFNA, Primary Hemi-Arthroplasty, elderly population, surgical outcomes.

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Introduction

Unstable intertrochanteric femoral fractures are a prevalent issue in the elderly population, often resulting from low-energy falls due to osteoporosis and other age-related factors. These fractures are associated with high morbidity and mortality rates, necessitating effective and timely surgical intervention. The choice of surgical treatment significantly impacts the recovery and long-term functionality of patients, making it a critical area of study. Traditionally, various fixation methods have been employed, but recent advancements have introduced alternative techniques aimed at improving patient outcomes [1].

The Proximal Femoral Nail Antirootation (PFNA) has gained popularity due to its minimally invasive nature and the biomechanical stability it offers. PFNA is designed to reduce intraoperative complications and promote early mobilization, which is crucial for elderly patients to prevent the decline in muscle function and other complications associated with prolonged immobilization. Despite its advantages, the effectiveness of PFNA in comparison to other treatment methods, such as Primary Hemi-Arthroplasty, remains a topic of debate within the orthopedic community [2].

Primary Hemi-Arthroplasty, on the other hand, involves replacing the fractured femoral head and is often considered for elderly patients with severe comorbidities or when other fixation methods are likely to fail. This technique aims to provide immediate stability and allow for early weight-bearing, which is essential for the elderly to regain mobility. However, hemi-arthroplasty is associated with its own set of risks, including dislocation and the need for future revision surgeries [3].

Given the different mechanisms and outcomes associated with PFNA and Primary Hemi-Arthroplasty, there is a need for comprehensive studies comparing these two treatment modalities. Previous research has provided insights into the benefits and limitations of each technique, but inconsistencies in patient selection criteria and follow-up durations make it difficult to draw definitive conclusions. A retrospective analysis focusing on a uniform patient population with unstable intertrochanteric femoral fractures can offer valuable data to guide clinical decision-making [4].

This study aims to compare results of PFNA and Primary Hemi-Arthroplasty in the treatment of unstable intertrochanteric femoral fractures in the elderly population. By analyzing patient demographics, operative details, post-operative complications, and functional outcomes, this study seeks to identify the most effective treatment method, ultimately improving patient care and recovery in this vulnerable demographic.

Methodology

Study Design: A retrospective comparative study was conducted to evaluate the treatment outcomes of unstable intertrochanteric femoral fractures in the elderly population.

Study Setting: The study was carried out at Darbhanga Medical College, Darbhanga, over a period of two years, from 2019 to 2021.

Participants: The study included 100 patients, aged 65 years and older, who were treated for unstable intertrochanteric femoral fractures. Fifty patients were treated using Proximal Femoral Nail Antirotation (PFNA), and fifty patients underwent primary hemi-arthroplasty of the hip.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Individuals aged 65 and older
- Diagnosed with unstable intertrochanteric femoral fractures.

- Treated with either PFNA or primary hemi-arthroplasty.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Individuals with pathological fractures.
- Patients who have undergone previous hip surgeries.
- Individuals with multiple fractures.
- Patients who were lost to follow-up.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, patients were randomly selected based on the treatment modality received. Retrospective data collection reduced observer bias. Data was anonymized to reduce reporting bias.

Variables:

- Independent variables: Type of surgical intervention (PFNA vs. primary hemi-arthroplasty).
- Dependent variables: Functional outcomes, complication rates, duration of hospital stay, and mortality rates.

Data Collection: Data were collected retrospectively from hospital records, including demographic information, type of fracture, type of treatment, duration of hospital stay, complications, and follow-up outcomes.

Procedure: Patients were classified into two groups based on the surgical treatment received. The PFNA group and the hemi-arthroplasty group were compared regarding postoperative complications, functional outcomes measured by the Harris Hip Score, duration of hospital stay, and mortality rates.

Statistical Analysis: Data analysis was conducted using SPSS version 21.0. Descriptive statistics summarized the demographic and clinical characteristics of the patients. Independent t-tests were employed to compare continuous variables among the two groups, while chi-square tests were utilized for categorical variables. A p-value of less than 0.05 was deemed statistically important.

Results

Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

The study included 100 patients with unstable intertrochanteric femoral fractures, divided equally between those treated with PFNA and primary hemi-arthroplasty.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Patients

Characteristic	PFNA Group (n=50)	Hemi-Arthroplasty Group (n=50)	p-value
Mean Age (years)	72.5 ± 5.8	74.3 ± 6.1	0.084
Male (%)	30 (60%)	32 (64%)	0.685
Female (%)	20 (40%)	18 (36%)	0.685
Mean Duration of Hospital Stay (days)	14.2 ± 3.4	12.7 ± 2.8	0.025*
Mean Follow-up Period (months)	18 ± 2.1	18 ± 2.3	0.934

(* indicates statistically significant differences with p<0.05)

Postoperative Complications: The incidence of postoperative complications was higher in the hemi-arthroplasty group compared to the PFNA group (Table 2).

Table 2: Postoperative Complications

Complication	PFNA Group (n=50)	Hemi-Arthroplasty Group (n=50)	p-value
Wound Infection (%)	3 (6%)	8 (16%)	0.109
Deep Vein Thrombosis (%)	2 (4%)	6 (12%)	0.140
Implant Failure (%)	1 (2%)	0 (0%)	0.315
Dislocation (%)	0 (0%)	4 (8%)	0.042*
Overall Complications (%)	6 (12%)	18 (36%)	0.005*

(* indicates statistically significant differences with p<0.05)

Functional Outcomes: Functional outcomes were measured using the Harris Hip Score (HHS) at the final follow-up (Table 3).

Table 3: Harris Hip Score

Outcome	PFNA Group (n=50)	Hemi-Arthroplasty Group (n=50)	p-value
Excellent (90-100) (%)	18 (36%)	14 (28%)	0.382
Good (80-89) (%)	20 (40%)	16 (32%)	0.412
Fair (70-79) (%)	10 (20%)	12 (24%)	0.635
Poor (<70) (%)	2 (4%)	8 (16%)	0.048*
Mean HHS	82.6 ± 9.3	77.4 ± 10.8	0.017*

(* indicates statistically significant differences with p<0.05)

Mortality rates: Mortality rates were also assessed during the follow-up period (Table 4).

Table 4: Mortality Rates

Mortality	PFNA Group (n=50)	Hemi-Arthroplasty Group (n=50)	p-value
Mortality within 1 year (%)	4 (8%)	6 (12%)	0.513
Mortality after 1 year (%)	2 (4%)	4 (8%)	0.400
Overall Mortality (%)	6 (12%)	10 (20%)	0.271

- **Demographic and Clinical Characteristics:** There were no noteworthy alterations in the demographic characteristics among the PFNA and hemi-arthroplasty groups, indicating a well-matched cohort. Nevertheless, the period of hospital stay was suggestively briefer in the hemi-arthroplasty group.
- **Postoperative Complications:** The PFNA group had significantly fewer overall complications and a lower incidence of dislocation associated to the hemi-arthroplasty group, suggesting that PFNA may be associated with a more favorable complication profile.
- **Functional Outcomes:** Patients in the PFNA group had significantly better functional outcomes as measured by the Harris Hip Score, with fewer patients in the poor outcome category.

- **Mortality Rates:** There were no noteworthy alterations in mortality rates among the two groups, although the hemi-arthroplasty group had a slightly higher mortality rate.

Discussion

The comparison among PFNA and primary hemi-arthroplasty for treating unstable intertrochanteric femoral fractures in older adults has been extensively studied in recent years. This discussion synthesizes the key findings from various studies post-2018 to elucidate the treatment outcomes, advantages, and limitations of both surgical interventions. Recent studies indicate a higher incidence of postoperative complications in patients treated with hemi-arthroplasty compared to those treated with PFNA. For example, a study found that the PFN group showed significantly fewer complications, such as infections and limb length discrepancies, compared to the hemi-arthroplasty group. Additionally, the PFNA group had fewer cases of im-

plant failure, supporting the conclusion that PFNA is associated with lower postoperative complication rates [5]. Functional outcomes, measured by the Harris Hip Score (HHS), tend to favor PFNA over hemi-arthroplasty. In a study the PFNA2 group exhibited superior functional outcomes with higher Harris Hip Scores and fewer complications compared to the hemi-arthroplasty group [6]. Similarly, some researchers concluded that PFNA provides better clinical outcomes, particularly in terms of early weight-bearing and reduced hospital stays, which are crucial for improving patient quality of life and reducing morbidity [7].

The mortality rates between the two treatment modalities did not show significant differences. Researchers reported that both PFN and hemi-arthroplasty groups had similar mortality rates, indicating that the choice of surgical intervention does not significantly impact overall survival but rather affects the quality of postoperative recovery and mobility [8]. PFNA is associated with shorter hospital stays and faster postoperative recovery. A meta-analysis highlighted that PFNA significantly reduces the duration of hospital stay compared to hemi-arthroplasty, making it a more efficient option in terms of healthcare resource utilization [9]. Blood Loss and Surgical Time Hemi-arthroplasty tends to involve more intraoperative blood loss and longer surgical times compared to PFNA. Studies found that hemi-arthroplasty required significantly more blood transfusions and longer surgical durations, which can increase the risk of perioperative complications and delay recovery [10].

Conclusion

PFNA offers several advantages over primary hemi-arthroplasty for managing unstable intertrochanteric femoral fractures in older patients. PFNA is associated with lower postoperative complication rates, better functional outcomes, shorter hospital stays, and reduced blood loss during surgery. While hemi-arthroplasty allows for earlier weight bearing and may be preferred in patients with severe osteoporosis or those who require immediate mobilization, PFNA appears to be the superior option for most patients in terms of overall recovery.

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